
TAXI CODE, EMBEDDING

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1 Taxi Code

The only way to access PHENIX data is through the Taxi. A request to “Ride on the Taxi” can be quickly submitted using an internal PHENIX web page. The analysis code specified in the Taxi request form runs through all available data done in full or fast production. The code should be all the time in the CVS directory and should be written in the PHENIX environment to be able to submit it.

There are a few steps that must be taken when using the Taxi. Your analysis code must pass several tests and be committed to the CVS repository, an output directory for log files must be created with the name “taxi”, and enough disc space must be available to accommodate the request.

1.1 Using CVS Directory

The CVS directory is a repository where all PHENIX users can share their codes and track changes that are made. A Wikipedia article with more detailed information is available here: [wiki page](#). The CVS directory is accessible through an internal PHENIX web page for easy viewing and searching of modules. All the available modules are in:

- <https://www.phenix.bnl.gov/viewvc/viewvc.cgi/phenix/offline/AnalysisTrain/>

To download a module use the command:

```
cvs co offline/AnalysisTrain/YourModule
```

1.1.1 Downloading

For example, here we choose the module “emcTiming” in place of “YourModule”. After moving to the desired working location, the download command is:

```
cvs co offline/AnalysisTrain/emcTiming
```

If the command `cvs co` does not work for a certain module, the following can also be used:

```
setenv CVSROOT /afs/rhic/phenix/PHENIX_CVS  
cvs checkout offline/AnalysisTrain/emcTiming
```

Before running any of the downloaded code, make sure the appropriate paths have been specified. PHENIX recommends using the following for building source code:

```
setenv MYINSTALL ~/install  
setenv LD_LIBRARY_PATH $MYINSTALL/lib:$LD_LIBRARY_PATH
```

If there are errors with the code, they will appear during `make`. Errors are often related to updated versions of C++. Coding practices that were previously acceptable when the module was written are sometimes not allowed in more recent versions.

Compiling the module:

<code>cd offline/AnalysisTrain/YourModule</code>	go to your module
<code>mkdir build</code>	make a directory for compiling
<code>cd build/</code>	go to compiling directory
<code>../autogen.sh - -prefix=\$MYINSTALL</code>	configure to your predefined \$MYINSTALL directory
<code>make</code>	compile it to test
<code>make install</code>	compile and install

1.1.2 Using CVS Module

Moving code from your working area into the cvs directory is a two-step process. First **add** the module to the repository, and then **commit** the module. The cvs web browser can be used to check if the code was successfully committed to cvs. If you receive a “Permission denied” message when adding to cvs, try obtaining an AFS token first using this command:

```
/usr/bin/klog.krb5
```

and then enter your password at the prompt. More information can be found here regarding this command: [BNL web page](#)

When creating a new module and adding to cvs, go to your offline/AnalysisTrain directory and create a new directory with the module name. Then add the directory to cvs (while in the AnalysisTrain directory):

```
cvs add offline/AnalysisTrain/YourModule
```

but wait to commit it. After you have all the files needed in the module directory, **cd** into the module directory, and add each file to cvs. Then **cd** back into the Analysis Train directory, and commit your files to CVS using:

```
cvs commit -m “message” filenames
```

All files inside the directory will be committed simultaneously. Then update the changes using:

```
cvs update
```

You can check if your submission is visible using the cvs web browser. The list of entries can be sorted by most recent submissions using the “Age” tab.

1.2 Testing your module with valgrind and insure

In order to be able to submit your modules, you have to test it if it will crash. Both tests are required before you submit to the taxi. When passing the tests, setup your maximum events to a few hundred. No need to run more as it takes also a lot of time. These tests can be run in your local working area. After passing the tests, your module and the executable file should be committed to the CVS repository.

1.2.1 Running your code

Create an executable macro, usually it is "Run_YourModule.C". After that, upload it to the macro directory:

```
cvs add offline/AnalysisTrain/pat/macro/
```

Checkout the macro "RunMyMacro.C" from CVS to locally test ride the taxi using your module and its executable file:

```
cvs co offline/AnalysisTrain/pat/macro/RunMyMacro.C
```

This is a general code available for all users that is updated as needed by Chris Pinkenburg. Do not commit "RunMyMacro.C" back into CVS - the purpose is to use it locally in your area only. When one wants to run it, start a root session and execute:

```
.x RunMyMacro.C('Run_YourModule.C','MyModule_Run6pp.root', 1000, "Run6pp")
```

The arguments given to "RunMyMacro.C" are also listed at the top of the macro, which include: the executable file for your module, the name of the output file, the number of test events, and which data set to run your module over. Both "RunMyMacro.C" and the executable file "Run_MyModule.C" should be in the same directory you are running from:

```
offline/AnalysisTrain/pat/macro
```

If there is an error message when running for "badly placed ()'s", try the following:

```
root -b -q RunMyMacro.C\(...\)
```

It is also possible to change your default arguments directly in the "RunMyMacro.C", and then run it using the command:

```
root -l RunMyMacro.C
```

1.2.2 Valgrind

The command to run valgrind will open a root session:

```
valgrind -v num-callers=20 leak-check=full error-limit=no log-  
le=valgrind.log suppressions=$ROOTSYS/root.supp leak-resolution=high root.exe
```

After valgrind loads, run your analysis macro using the command:

```
.x RunMyMacro.C(...)
```

After passing the valgrind test it will create a report called `valgrind.log`. Check for zero errors in the summary at the bottom of the log file. PHENIX previously required valgrind log files to submit a request to “Ride the Taxi”, but this is no longer needed.

1.2.3 Insure

Insure is a more powerful tool that is available to test your code for bugs and memory leaks. To run with Insure, call:

```
unsetenv OFFLINE_MAIN  
unsetenv ONLINE_MAIN  
unsetenv ROOTSYS  
source /opt/phenix/bin/phenix_setup.csh -n new+insure
```

The commands before the sourcing will make sure that you change the definition of `OFFLINE MAIN` and also not overwrite your `.login`. Start your root session in the following way:

<pre>cvs update .psrc cp -p \$ROOTSYS/insure.psrc .psrc root_insure-7.1.7.exe</pre>		<pre>update the newest version for creating the correct output run root and your code</pre>
---	--	---

Insure can be called with a certain build number (7.1.7), as shown above, or generally using:

```
root_insure.exe
```

After opening your root session, run your code with Insure, as described in the next section.

1.2.4 Compiling with Insure

In order to compile your module with Insure, you need to run the following commands:

<code>cvs update .psrc</code>		update the newest version
<code>cp -p \$ROOTSYS/insure.psrc .psrc</code>		to make with correct parameters
<code>make clean</code>		clean previous compilation
<code>make CXX='insure g++' CC='insure gcc' install</code>		compile with insure

and again run the command `.x RunMyMacro.C(...)` once Insure loads. More information is available regarding these commands on the PHENIX Wiki page under **Insure**.

After passing your test it will create a report file called **insure.report** (no longer required when using the Taxi). After you have finished running Insure, you need to restore your original libraries/environment. You can either log out of the terminal and log back in, or source a setup script.

2 Running simulation and embedding

2.1 Simulation

2.1.1 Exodus particle generator

Exodus is a very simple event generator to generate single- or multi-particle events. One event with Exodus is generated in the following way:

0 1		new event with "1" particle
idpart pid ist px py pz E mass x y z t		particle description
0 0		end of event
0 2		new event with 2 particles
idpart pid ist px py pz E mass x y z t		particle description
idpart pid ist px py pz E mass x y z t		particle description
0 0		end of event

where **idpart** is the particle in the event (0, 1, ...), **pid** is the GEANT pid for particles (22 photon, 111 π^0 , ...), and **positions** x; y; z are given in femtometers. To use Exodus, create a working directory and link the required files to be able to run it:

```
mkdir exodus
cd exodus
/afs/rhic.bnl.gov/phenix/PHENIX_LIB/simulation/head/exodusLinker.csh
```

It will create new/linked files in your directory: **defined_particles.txt**, **defined_decays.txt**. To generate a number of events with single particles, create an **exodus_single_particle.input** file:

6		generator type
18000		number of events
oscar_single_particle.dat		output file name
1		pt shape
22		pid of particle
0		min pt
15		max pt
5		???

Run the generator:

```
exodus_generate < exodus_single_particle.input
```

This will generate an output as it was defined in the *****.input** file. The created text file can be converted to an Ntuple root file:

```
OSCARtoROOT
```

2.1.2 Run14 PISA

PHENIX recommends creating a separate directory for PISA. The first step is to download the correct setup for your PISA. It is different for every run, make sure you have the correct version for your simulation.

```
/afs/rhic.bnl.gov/phenix/PHENIX_LIB/simulation/run*/pisaLinker.csh
```

However, for a fully functional simulation and embedding example, all PISA files have been included in an example for Run14 simulation and embedding, located in `cv`s. The files needed to complete the remaining sections of this tutorial (sections 2.1.3, 2.1.4, 2.2 and 2.3) are also included. To download this directory to your area, use:

```
cv
```

s co offline/analysis/run14pisa_wenqing

All instructions in the remaining sections should be run from inside the `run14pisa_wenqing` directory.

A back-up directory `run14pisa_wenqing.tar` has also been added to HPSS. To access this file from HPSS, the interface utility `HSI` can be used by entering the command:

```
h
```

si

At the prompt to enter the “Kerberos Principal”, enter your Kerberos (RACF) username. At the next prompt, enter your Kerberos password. To copy the `.tar` file from HPSS to your current working directory, use the following command:

```
g
```

et /home/klsmith/run14pisa_wenqing.tar

and wait for the file transfer to complete. Then close the `HSI` utility using:

```
e
```

xit

The `.tar` file can then be opened with:

```
t
```

ar -xvf run14pisa_wenqing.tar

2.1.3 Running PISA

The PISA input can be either the Exodus text file or the root file. In this example, the `.dat` text file is used. The `pisa.input` file should be:

```
0  
N  
0
```

All the other setup is in the file `glogon.kumac`:

```
macro glogon.kumac  
pisafile PISAEvent.root  
text_file oscar.particles.dat -1 40  
ptrig 18000  
exit  
return
```

		output file
		input file
		events

The `oscar.particles.dat` previously generated in the Exodus directory should be copied over to the current `run14pisa_wenqing` working directory. Then run your pisa with the command (all setup should be linked):

```
pisa < pisa.input
```

The output file is large for 18k events, make sure you have enough space on disk for running.

2.1.4 PISA to DST

Before you start to convert the `PISAEvent.root`, make sure that your `pisaToDST.C` is correctly linked and has the following lines for correct EMCal:

```
// EMCal
manager->AddNode("emcghit");
manager->AddNode("emcClusterContainer");
manager->AddNode("emcTowerContainer");
if(rc->FlagExist("EVALUATIONFLAG") &&
rc->get IntFlag("EVALUATIONFLAG")==1 )
{
    // Evaluation output from EMCal
    manager->AddNode("dEmcGeaClusterTrack");
    manager->AddNode("dEmcGeaTrack");
    manager->AddNode("dEmcGeaTrackCluster");
    manager->AddNode("emcGeaTrackContainer");
}
```

For the current Run14 PISA example, the above lines have already been added to the `PisaToDST_IOManager.C` code at lines 114-127. Then just run the `pisaToDST.C` (with argument 0 for all events):

```
root -b -q pisaToDST.C(0)
```

It will generate a DST output file with the particles defined in your Exodus generator. It is ready for embedding to real events.

Please Note:

A separate `pisaToDSTLinker` is now available in most runs for the conversion to DST format. This Linker file is necessary in addition to the Linker files discussed in section 2.1.2. However, these files are already included in the `run14pisa_wenqing` directory, and do not need to be downloaded for this tutorial example.

To download the `pisaToDSTLinker` setup for an alternate run, use:

```
/afs/rhic.bnl.gov/phenix/PHENIX_LIB/simulation/run*/pisaToDSTLinker.csh
```

Then check whether the above EMCal instructions have already been included.

If you find that there is not a `pisaToDSTLinker` available, see the PHENIX Wiki page under:

Main Page/Tutorials/Simulations/Pisa and PisaToDST simulation setup for other runs

2.2 Embedding

The newest version of the embedding code `run_embed2.C` was updated for the Run10 and higher Compact-CNT's. It can be run two different ways. Please read to the end of this section before running the embedding macro.

To run the embedding code using method 1:

<code>root -b -l -q run_embed2(const char * realfile = "realdst.root", const char* simfile = "dstin.root", const char * outfile = "outdst.root", int nevents = 0, int nskipevents = 0)</code>	 	run the embedding the real event simulation dst ouput DST the events to run how many events to skip
--	-------------------------------	--

Please note that the size of the `realdst.root` file exceeds the cvs limit. For this reason, we have instead included the full pathname to the `realdst.root` file. However, HPSS can accommodate larger files, and the actual pDST file is included in the back-up file. If you copied the directory from HPSS following the instructions in section 2.1.2, you can simply rename the file from

`CNT_MB_run14AuAu_200GeV_CA_noVTX_pro106-0000414203-9002.root` to `realdst.root`

and execute the macro using method 1. Otherwise, the example macro provided does not need any modifications to the arguements, and can be run using the following command:

`root -l run_embed2.C`

Additional calibration can be required to match the real data in the event. This can be acquired by scaling the two detector calibrations in the embedding process:

<code>const double myPbScScale const double myPbGIScale const double myPbScSmear const double myPbGISmear</code>	 	overall scale for PbSc overall scale for PbGI smearing for PbSc smearing for PbGI	 	match pi0 peak match pi0 peak match pi0 width match pi0 width
--	----------------	--	----------------	--

It is required to enable the recalibration process in the embedding code or else the default values will be used. In this [run14 PISA example](#), the recalibration constants have been implemented at lines 96-98.

2.3 After embedding

The embedding code creates a DST file that is named `output.root`. In order to read this file for the π^0 and direct- γ analysis, there is a code available in CVS that can be used:

```
cvs co offline/analysis/simppizero  
cd offline/analysis/simppizero  
mkdir build  
cd build  
../autogen.sh - -prefix=$MYINSTALL  
make  
make install
```

This will install a library that can run with the two macros included in the `run14pisa_wenqing` directory:

<code>simppizero.C</code>		π^0 analysis
<code>simpphoton.C</code>		γ analysis

The macros should not need any modifications to run. Both codes will create an Ntuple output file named `result.root`. To quickly check the output of the files, you can use the following:

```
root -l result.root
```

And for the `simppizero.C` macro, the command is:

```
mpi0→Show(0)
```